

ISic0934

I.Sicily inscription 0934

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Δεκεμβρίω □: letter β at the end of line 2; letters ρω at the beginning of line 3; chi-rho at the beginning of line 4

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ζόδωρος

2. ἀπὸ Μά

3. κρης κώ

4. μηνς ἔτε

5. λεύτησε

6. μηνὶ Δε

7. κεμ

8. β

9. ρίω

9a. □

Apparatus

Text of IG

Kaibel: extremi vocabuli litteras βρω vv. 2 et 3 scriptas repperit Momms.

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492564

EDCS 39102091

PHI 140415

Bibliography

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1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 36.1279.E.2

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0934. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340114>